

ALTERNATIVE LEARNING SYSTEM (ALS) LEARNERS LITERACY ACQUISITION IN SELECTED BUREAU OF JAIL MANAGEMENT AND PENOLOGY (BJMP) IN CAVITE PROVINCE: AN ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to investigate the literacy acquisition among Alternative Learning System (ALS) learners within selected Bureau of Jail Management and Penology (BJMP) facilities in Cavite Province in the municipality of Tanza and Carmona in the school year 2022-2023. The research employs a descriptive approach and includes an adopted and modified survey questionnaire based on Functional Literacy, Education and Mass Media Survey as a primary tool to gather the data and standardized literacy assessments tool based on Post Functional Literacy Test (FLT). Findings revealed that BJMP learner's literacy acquisition manifest closely moving towards the mastery level needed to face the globalized literacy challenges and skills. Moreover a diverse learners' profile highlights the unique barriers faced by ALS learners within the correctional system. Factors such as limited access to educational resources and the psychological impact of incarceration emerge as critical determinants influencing literacy acquisition. In addition, the findings serve as basis for the development of sustainable activities tailored to the specific needs of ALS learners within the correctional context and the establishment of support systems that foster a conducive learning environment for incarcerated individuals pursuing literacy through ALS program specifically in digital citizenship, scientific and critical thinking skills and mathematical and problem solving skills where they got the lowest score in FLT. Finally, the researchers suggest further exploration of literacy acquisition of Person Deprived of Liberty (PDL) among BJMP ALS learners in other municipalities and perform

a comparative study to see if the result/findings represent the general situation of BJMP ALS learners in the Division of Cavite Province Alternative Learning System.

Keywords: *Functional Literacy Test, Literacy, Program, Development, Acquisition*

INTRODUCTION

The literacy acquisition of Alternative Learning System (ALS) learners within the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology (BJMP) in Cavite Province serves as a critical nexus between education and the rehabilitation of incarcerated individuals. The significance of implementing sustainable literacy activities within correctional facilities lies in the transformative potential of education to break the cycle of recidivism and equip inmates with essential skills for successful reintegration into society. Many inmates within the BJMP in Cavite Province may not have had the opportunity to complete formal education due to various circumstances. The ALS program offers a lifeline to these individuals, empowering them with literacy skills that are fundamental for effective communication, critical thinking, and personal development. By addressing the educational gaps of inmates, we aim to contribute to their sense of self-worth and agency.

Literacy acquisition through the ALS program can provide inmates with the tools necessary to seek employment, engage in positive social interactions, and make informed decisions upon reentry into society. Sustainable literacy activities within the BJMP are important, therefore, a strategic investment in breaking the cycle of incarceration and fostering a path towards rehabilitation. In addition, education is not only a means to acquire knowledge but also a catalyst for personal growth and well-being. Literacy skills contribute to an individual's ability to express themselves, understand their rights and responsibilities, and engage in continuous learning. Sustainable literacy activities in correctional facilities can create a positive and constructive environment that supports the psychological and emotional well-being of inmates. Equipping inmates with literacy skills goes beyond the confines of correctional facilities. It serves as a foundation for their successful reintegration into the community. Inmates who have undergone literacy programs are better positioned to contribute meaningfully to society, whether through gainful employment, community service, or positive engagement with their families.

Most countries in Southeast Asia and Africa has been identified as the most impediment country in terms of economic development hit by economic crisis bought by poverty which is link to illiteracy. Philippines is not exempted in economic crisis bought about poverty as one of the member of Southeast Asia Countries with the highest poverty rates, out-of-school Children (OSCs), out-of-school youth (OSYs) and out-of-school Adult (OSCs) were group by poverty, owing lack of educational opportunities cause by illiteracy (Apao et.al, 2014).

Moreover, section 2 of RA 9155 highlights the function of the Alternative Learning System (ALS) in providing free and compulsory education to Out-of-school youth and adults. A parallel education learning system in the Philippines provides opportunities for out-of-school youth and adult (OSYA) school leavers to access equivalent pathways to complete basic education. ALS education is designed to meet the educational needs of schools dropouts, adults, and other disadvantaged learners who do not have access to formal education; many who are: deprived, depressed, and underserved as described by the legislation (DepEd, 2016).

Furthermore, since 1990, the literature has shown that prisoners who attend educational programs while they are incarcerated are less likely to return to prison following their release (Greenberg, 2008). Studies in several States have indicated that recidivism rates have declined where inmates have received an appropriate education. In addition, the right kind of educational program leads to less violence by inmates involved in the programs and a more positive prison environment (Vacca, 2004). Allowing for behavioral changes inside prisons necessarily implies education. In Thailand, the point is not only to organize professional training courses but also to make detainees aware of the fact that they belong to a community of values. Non-formal education allows the necessary flexibility to an individual approach of training that must take into account the particular needs of learners.

In international context, the involvement of all the staff working in prison, as well as the training of the teaching staff, are the essential lines of policies currently developed in Thai prisons (Phatininnart, 2009). Participation in educational activities by the imprisoned group mostly depends on the desirable needs and interests of the convicts themselves - whether they wish to upgrade their educational background or see the benefit of education for improving their quality of lives. Some of them have realized to the fact that due to their poor education they have tended to be misled by ill-disposed individuals, or have been taken advantage of by other, more strong-willed people (Phatininnart, 2009).

According to Jacobi (2008), research on incarceration and educational access continues to reveal the stark reality for many adjudicated youth: without access to educational opportunities recidivism is probable. Yet conventional methods of teaching critical reading, writing, and thinking skills are not always successful for juveniles who have found little success (or hope) in traditional schooling. Jacobi argues that alternative literacy practices can effectively supplement conventional general education and vocational training courses by engaging juveniles through creativity, critical self-awareness, and a shift in how audience and authorship is understood.

Similarly to the study of Romoroza (2019), reading comprehension is one of the problems encountered by learners in the field of reading in Alternative Learning System Cantilan District Jail in terms of identifying the main idea of the selection resulting to poor reading comprehension.

Objectives of the Study

The study aims to:

1. Identify the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. Age;
 - b. Gender;
 - c. Civil Status;
2. Identify the respondents functional literacy acquisition along six (6) learning strand and;
3. What are the demographical differences of the respondents based on their literacy acquisition?

METHODOLOGY

Sampling

This research study employs a descriptive approach research design involving all learners enrolled in Alternative Learning System in school year 2022-2023 in the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology (BJMP) in the municipalities of Tanza and Carmona City. Previous school year and learners and other municipalities are not included in the study.

Data Collection

The research also includes a modified survey questionnaire based on Functional Literacy, Education and Mass Media Survey as a primary tool to gather the data and standardized literacy assessments based on Post Functional Literacy Test (FLT) administered to all ALS learners.

Ethical Issue

Confidentiality of all information is used for research purposes only.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1. Demographic profile distribution of respondents

Variable		Frequency (N=140)	Percentage
Sex	Male	107	76.43
	Female	23	23.57
Age	15	0	0
	16-20	9	6.43

	21-30	65	46.43
	31 above	66	47.14
Civil Status			
	Single	53	37.86
	Married	85	60.71
	Widow	2	1.43

Table 1 shows the demographic profile distribution of the respondent. The data revealed that 76.43% were male and 23.57% were female; thus, most of BJMP ALS learners in two municipalities were male. As the age distribution, the data shows that respondent with the age 31 above have the highest frequency of 47.14%; 46.43% has an age of 21-30, 6.43% has an age of 16-20. In terms of civil status, the data shown that most of the respondent is married with 60.71%, 37.86% are single and 1.43% is widow. This respondent's demographic characteristic was identical to the similar studies on ALS learners (Ocampo, 2021).

Table 2 shows the Alternative Learning System Post Functional Literacy Assessment skills in elementary level in two BJMP facilities in Cavite Province (Tanza and Carmona City) for school year 2022-2023. The result revealed that the level of ALS learners acquisition based on functional literacy test is under moving towards mastery. It implies that the ALS learners enrolled in the elementary level manifest the literacy skills moving toward mastery level. The result shows that understanding self and society have the highest acquisition by the learners with 90.00% mean percentage score. This implies further that the youth and adult learners supports for understanding the society and shaped by their experiences and best learning comes from their personal experiences and society. Moreover, communication skills in English got the least mean percentage score with 63.25% mean percentage score, the result revealed that Elementary learners has an average literacy skills in terms of communication specifically in English language followed by Learning Strand Filipino and Digital Citizenship got the lowest mean percentage score.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistic on the Functional Literacy Assessment of ALS Learners in Elementary Level in three Municipalities based on Mean Percentage Score

Functional Literacy Skills	MPS	Description
LS 1 - Communication Skills - English	63.25%	Average
LS 1 - Communication Skills – Filipino	79.64%	Moving Towards Mastery
LS 2 - Scientific and Critical Thinking Skills	88.50%	Moving Towards Mastery
LS 3 - Mathematical and Problem-Solving Skills	83.44%	Moving Towards Mastery
LS 4 - Life and Career Skills	85.83%	Moving Towards Mastery
LS 5 - Understanding Self and Society	90.00%	Closely Approximating Mastery
LS 6 - Digital Citizenship	81.25%	Moving Towards Mastery
Total	81.70	Moving Towards Mastery

Legend: based on Descriptive Equivalent on mastery/achievement – DepEd Memo No. 160, s.2012

MPS	Descriptive Equivalent
96-100%	Mastered
86-95%	Closely Approximating Mastery

66-85%	<i>Moving Towards Mastery</i>
35-65%	<i>Average</i>
15-34%	<i>Low</i>
5-14%	<i>Very Low</i>
0-4%	<i>Absolutely no Mastery</i>

Table 3. Descriptive Statistic on the Functional Literacy Assessment of ALS Learners in Junior High School level in three Municipalities based on Mean Percentage Score

Functional Literacy Skills	MPS	Description
LS 1- Communication Skills - English	78.67	Moving Towards Mastery
LS 1- Communication Skills – Filipino	76.00	Moving Towards Mastery
LS 2 - Scientific and Critical Thinking Skills	64.50	Moving Towards Mastery
LS 3 - Mathematical and Problem-Solving Skills	77.17	Moving Towards Mastery
LS 4 - Life and Career Skills	85.00	Moving Towards Mastery
LS 5 - Understanding Self and Society	92.00	Closely Approximating Mastery
LS 6 - Digital Citizenship	78.00	Moving Towards Mastery
Total	78.76	Moving Towards Mastery

Legend: based on Descriptive Equivalent on mastery/achievement – DepEd Memo No. 160, s.2012

MPS	Descriptive Equivalent
96-100%	<i>Mastered</i>
86-95%	<i>Closely Approximating Mastery</i>
66-85%	<i>Moving Towards Mastery</i>
35-65%	<i>Average</i>
15-34%	<i>Low</i>
5-14%	<i>Very Low</i>
0-4%	<i>Absolutely no Mastery</i>

Table 3 presents the Junior High School literacy skills in two Bureau of Jail Management and Penology (BJMP) in the municipalities in Cavite Province for school year 2022-2023. The findings revealed that the Junior High School level learners acquisition of functional literacy skills under moving towards mastery. The results shows that learning strand 5 or Understanding self and Society got the highest mean percentage score with 92.00% closely approximating mastery level. In terms of least mastered literacy skills, the findings shows scientific and critical thinking skills learning strand 3 with the score of 64.50% followed by mathematical and problem solving skills, communication skills and digital citizenship, this implies that the Junior High Schools learners need to further enhance those functional literacy skills.

Moreover, the mean percentage score result both elementary and junior high school level learners literacy skills must be addressed by ALS implementers by developing localized instructional material and program to highlight the skills acquisition and knowledge and provide more hands-on experiences to adult learners to gain practical experiences with the supervision of ALS specialist, schools supervisor, jail officer through the enhancement ALS program for person deprived of liberty.

Demographic differences of the respondents based on their Functional Literacy Acquisition for Elementary level

When classified by sex, the result shows that communications skills, scientific and critical thinking skills, mathematical and problem solving skills, life and career skills, understanding self and society and digital citizenship do not vary significantly shown in table 4.

Table 4. Significant differences on literacy skills of ALS BJMP Learners when group according to sex

Functional Literacy Skills	n	t-value	p-value
LS 1 - Communication Skills - English	40	1.23	0.212
LS 1 - Communication Skills – Filipino	40	0.97	0.321
LS 2 - Scientific and Critical Thinking Skills	40	1.35	0.153
LS 3 - Mathematical and Problem-Solving Skills	40	-0.03	0.965
LS 4 - Life and Career Skills	40	-0.23	0.604
LS 5 - Understanding Self and Society	40	0.92	0.302
LS 6 - Digital Citizenship	40	-1.01	0.310

Table 5. Significant differences on literacy skills of ALS BJMP Learners when group according to age

Functional Literacy Skills	n	t-value	p-value
LS 1 - Communication Skills - English	40	-1.079	0.281
LS 1 - Communication Skills – Filipino	40	-0.585	0.555
LS 2 - Scientific and Critical Thinking Skills	40	-1.562	0.117
LS 3 - Mathematical and Problem-Solving Skills	40	-0.112	0.907
LS 4 - Life and Career Skills	40	3.304	0.001
LS 5 - Understanding Self and Society	40	-0.660	0.503
LS 6 - Digital Citizenship	40	0.976	0.321

Moreover, table 5 shows the significant differences on the functional literacy skills of ALS when group according to age. When group by age, the findings shows that communication skills, scientific and critical thinking skills, problem solving skills, understanding self and society and digital citizenship do not vary significantly. However, life and career skills have significant with p-value 0.001 when group according to age. Adult learners between 21-30 years old have bearing in the acquisition of literacy specifically in terms of life and career skills.

Table 6. Significant differences on literacy skills of ALS BJMP Learners when group according to civil status

Functional Literacy Skills	n	t-value	p-value
LS 1 - Communication Skills - English	40	0.542	0.204
LS 2 - Communication Skills – Filipino	40	0.666	0.501
LS 3 - Scientific and Critical Thinking Skills	40	0.245	0.803
LS 4 - Mathematical and Problem-Solving Skills	40	1.404	0.160
LS 5 - Life and Career Skills	40	0.890	0.372
LS 6 - Understanding Self and Society	40	-0.570	0.566
LS 7 - Digital Citizenship	40	0.307	0.755

In terms of civil status in table 6, the result reveals that communication skill – Filipino and English, scientific and critical thinking skills, mathematical and problem solving skills, life and career skills, understanding self and society and digital citizenship do not vary significantly.

Demographic differences of the respondents based on their Functional Literacy Acquisition for Junior High School level

Table 7 shows the significant differences on functional literacy skills of Junior High School level when group according to sex. The result revealed that communication skills, mathematical and problem solving skills, life and career skills, understanding self and society do not vary significantly. On the other hand, scientific and critical thinking skills and digital citizenship have significant differences when group according to sex.

Table 7. Significant differences on the functional literacy skills of Alternative Learning System Learners when group according to sex

Functional Literacy Skills	n	t-value	p-value
LS 1- Communication Skills - English	100	-1.031	0.302
LS 1 - Communication Skills – Filipino	100	1.555	0.120
LS 2 - Scientific and Critical Thinking Skills	100	3.156	0.001
LS 3 - Mathematical and Problem-Solving Skills	100	0.593	0.552
LS 4 - Life and Career Skills	100	-0.271	0.786
LS 5 - Understanding Self and Society	100	1.835	0.066
LS 6 - Digital Citizenship	100	2.235	0.003

Table 8 shows the significant differences on functional literacy skills of Junior High School level when group according to age. The result revealed that all learning strand do not vary significantly on the literarily acquisition of ALS learners. However, there is a gap in digital citizenship skills. Young learners between 15 to 20 years old have the highest rate of information and communication integration in their literacy skills.

Table 8. Significant differences on the functional literacy skills of Alternative Learning System Learners when group according to age

Functional Literacy Skills	n	t-value	p-value
LS 1 - Communication Skills - English	100	1.513	0.131
LS 1 - Communication Skills – Filipino	100	1.109	0.268
LS 2 - Scientific and Critical Thinking Skills	100	1.048	0.295
LS 3 - Mathematical and Problem-Solving Skills	100	1.894	0.059
LS 4 - Life and Career Skills	100	1.271	0.204
LS 5 - Understanding Self and Society	100	1.983	0.048
LS 6 - Digital Citizenship	100	-2.176	0.030

Table 9 shows the significant differences on functional literacy skills of Junior High School level when group according to civil status. The result revealed that all learning strand do not vary significantly.

Table 9. Significant differences on the functional literacy skills of Alternative Learning System Learners when group according to civil status

Functional Literacy Skills	n	t-value	p-value
LS 1- Communication Skills - English	100	-0.855	0.393
LS 1 - Communication Skills – Filipino	100	-0.187	0.852
LS 2 - Scientific and Critical Thinking Skills	100	1.082	0.280
LS 3 - Mathematical and Problem-Solving Skills	100	-2.246	0.025
LS 4 - Life and Career Skills	100	0.886	0.376
LS 5 - Understanding Self and Society	100	-0.212	0.832
LS 6 - Digital Citizenship	100	0.880	0.379

Conclusions

The functional literacy skills acquisition of Person Deprived of Liberty (PDL) BJMP learners in two municipalities in the province of Cavite specifically in Tanza and Carmona was investigated. Since the PDL learners attainment of their functional literacy skills based on Functional Literacy Test is generally moving towards the mastery, the research findings revealed that PDL ALS learners do not have the complete mastery skills acquisition literacy needed to face 21st century learners and globalized world challenges. The significant contributions of this study highlight and shows how ALS learners are progressing in their learning towards the literacy mastery skills, which will serve a baseline data, foundation of ALS Cavite Province for policy, strategic and intervention to help PDL ALS students to cope with the challenges in terms of 21st century learners and globalization. The study also finds that sex, age, and civil status impact the acquisition of PDL ALS learners' functional literacy skills in two municipalities in Cavite province.

Finally, the study adds to the body of knowledge on BJMP ALS, non formal education and also to literacy coordinating in terms of BJMP adult education, the second chance education but not a second class by shedding light on the current state and situation of Alternative Learning System, specifically in the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology in Cavite Province and also in the Philippines, in terms of promoting youth and adult literacy skills on person deprived of liberty (PDL). More specifically, the findings added to existing findings and studies on evaluating and assessing Alternative Learning System program and project by providing new perspectives and recommendations. A possible expansion of this study will be look at the ALS implementors skills and competencies.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the researchers recommend: a strong partnership, linkages in government and private institution that provide extension activity and project to assist ALS learners in improving their functional literacy skills, specifically in communication skills, digital citizenship, mathematical and problem solving skills and scientific and critical thinking skills. And given that the current study was conducted in two Bureau of Jail Management and Penology in two municipalities in Cavite Province, it may be worthwhile to investigate the Functional Literacy Skills of BJMP ALS learners in the 18 municipalities and 3 cities in the Division of Cavite Province and perform a comparative study to see if

the results/findings represent the general situation of BJMP ALS learners in the Division of Cavite Province Alternative Learning System.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers informed the respondent of the purpose of the study, that the latter's participation was voluntary and confidentiality of information was ensured. The respondent's anonymity was guaranteed. They may opt to participate or not by answering the survey questionnaire, the data was collected onsite through District ALS Coordinator and ALS teachers. The respondents expressed their thoughts freely and confidently. There was no conflict of interest since the researchers did not handle the learning session of the respondents. The data collected were respected and kept private and will be disposed when no longer needed.

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